

iAtlantic

INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT OF ATLANTIC
MARINE ECOSYSTEMS IN SPACE AND TIME

Research Highlights

The iAtlantic Consortium

The University of Edinburgh, UK (Coordinator)
Fundacao Universidade do Vale do Itajai, Brazil
University of the Western Cape, South Africa
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas, Spain
IMAR - Instituto do Mar, Azores, Portugal
Seascope Consultants Ltd, UK
Institut Francais de Recherche pour L'exploitation de la Mer, France
United Kingdom Research and Innovation, UK
Helmholtz Center for Ocean Research Kiel, Germany
Heriot-Watt University, UK
Universität Bremen, Germany
Universidade de Sao Paulo, Brazil
University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa
The Scottish Association for Marine Science, UK
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Cientificas y Tecnicas, Argentina
University College Cork - National University of Ireland, Cork, Ireland
Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo, Brazil
Nelson Mandela University, South Africa

Göteborgs Universitet, Sweden
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Brazil
University of Cape Town, South Africa
Seascope Belgium, Belgium
TMG Research gGmbH, Germany
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
Sorbonne University, France
Aarhus Universitet, Denmark
Alfred-Wegenerinstitut Helmholtzzentrum Für Polar-Und Meeresforschung, Germany
University College London, UK
Hafrannsknastofnun, Rannsókná-Og Radgjafarstofnun Hafs Og Vatna, Iceland
Temple University of The Commonwealth System of Higher Education, USA
Gianni Matthew, The Netherlands
National Research Foundation, South Africa
Oregon State University, USA
National Oceanography Centre, UK
Senckenberg Gesellschaft Für Naturforschung, Germany
Universitat de Barcelona, Spain

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This report was written by the following team on behalf of the iAtlantic consortium: J.M. Roberts, A. Biastoch, B. Boteler, M. Carreiro-Silva, T. Collart, C.W. Devey, A. Gebruk, V. Gunn, L-A. Henry, V.A.I. Huvenne, D. Jollivet, M. Matabos, T. Morato, M. Naumann & A.K. Sweetman. Compilation, layout, editing and design by V. Gunn.

Cover image: Cold-water coral assemblage on a vertical wall in the Whittard Canyon, NE Atlantic. Image courtesy NOC/JC237.

iAtlantic Research Highlights

Contents

Welcome	3
iAtlantic: A health check for Atlantic ecosystems.....	4
Summary of project results and achievements.....	7
Atlantic oceanography and ecosystem connectivity	7
Mapping Atlantic ecosystems.....	12
Drivers of ecosystem change and tipping point.....	18
Impact of multiple stressors on Atlantic ecosystems.....	24
Spatial and temporal management and protection	28
Data management and visualisation	33
Sharing knowledge, building capacity	35
Technology and innovation	39
Impact and relevance of results.....	41
Parting words.....	49
References.....	51
iAtlantic project deliverables	52
List of acronyms.....	53

Welcome

The iAtlantic project set out to complete one of the largest assessments of deep and open ocean ecosystems across both space and time ever attempted. We wanted not only to advance scientific understanding but to feed that knowledge directly to policy makers at national, regional and international levels. To do this we selected 12 study areas around the Atlantic basin and assembled a team of dedicated ocean experts across Argentina, Brazil, Canada, the European Union, South Africa, the UK and USA.

When we launched iAtlantic in Edinburgh in June 2019 we could not imagine that within a year the world would be gripped by a global pandemic that not only prevented research ships sailing but closed laboratories and curtailed meetings. We responded to the crisis by carefully conserving our resources and were fortunate to be able to extend the project duration for an additional 10 months. While we couldn't recover all the lost time and opportunities, we have been able to achieve the vast majority of our goals.

In this report we've summarised some of the major outcomes from our work. iAtlantic has made substantial contributions to our understanding of ocean ecosystem function in a rapidly changing ocean, including work that gives new insight into the implication of emerging human uses of the ocean such as deep-sea mineral mining. iAtlantic coincided with the final negotiations of the new UN 'High Seas' treaty, a new legally binding agreement to manage biodiversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction. Much of the work in this report is directly relevant to the science needed to underpin the successful implementation of the treaty, and in October 2023 iAtlantic and partners convened the first High Seas Treaty Symposium. As iAtlantic concludes at the end of March 2024, discussions for a second meeting are underway.

iAtlantic was a team effort, and when the team includes almost 200 researchers from 16 nations and overseas territories it's very hard to select the highlights in a summary report. I hope you enjoy the selection we've made and please visit the iAtlantic website where you can access the full portfolio of results and outputs.

Huge thanks to the iAtlantic family for all the hard work since 2019.

J Murray Roberts
iAtlantic Coordinator
March 2024

Acknowledgements & thanks

The core of the iAtlantic family includes over 200 researchers from the 36 organisations that form the project consortium, from students and early career scientists to senior academics, but the work conducted by iAtlantic would not have been possible without the many collaborators that we have.

We want to thank all those colleagues who have helped iAtlantic in many different ways: subcontractors, technicians, vessel crews and pilots, research and finance administration, legal and other professional services and many others. We are also grateful to all our partners, associated partners and stakeholders, who truly are essential for bringing our results into policy discussions and management practices! A special thank you to our Advisory Board and Science Council for their wise and insightful guidance. Final thanks are reserved for the European Commission and in particular the Horizon 2020 programme that enabled this Consortium to come to life.

A health check for Atlantic ecosystems

The ocean faces enormous challenges: climate change is affecting marine ecosystems that are already stressed by habitat destruction, pollution and overexploitation. Changes are apparent in seawater circulation patterns, temperature, acidity and oxygen levels – all of which have consequences for marine life.

Over the next century, the magnitude and rates of environmental change in the deep and open Atlantic Ocean are expected to be faster and more severe in some areas than others, and may be further exacerbated by human activities. But we know very little about exactly where, or when, the worst impacts of a changing ocean will occur.

Funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, iAtlantic undertook an ocean-wide approach to understanding the factors that control the distribution, stability and vulnerability of ecosystems in the Atlantic Ocean. Our work aimed to determine the tipping points - the points of irreversible change - for deep and open-ocean ecosystems, identify which drivers are most crucial in propelling ecosystems towards those tipping points, and understand what factors influence and support ecosystem resilience to environmental change.

iAtlantic has five key objectives (Fig 1). To achieve these, iAtlantic developed an integrated approach based on six research priorities:

1. Integrating basin-scale observation, modelling and genetic approaches to understand Atlantic oceanography and ecosystem connectivity;
2. Improving ecosystem mapping;
3. Identifying potential drivers of ecosystem change and tipping points in deep and open ocean ecosystems;
4. Understanding compound impacts of multiple stressors including warming, acidification and deoxygenation;
5. Enhancing spatial and temporal management and protection;
6. Sharing knowledge and building capacity, including promoting research from the global South through investment and engagement.

For more details about the iAtlantic approach see Roberts et al. 2023.

Figure 1: The iAtlantic objectives

iAtlantic focused its ecosystem assessment efforts on 12 key areas of the Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 2), selected on the basis of their international conservation significance and interest to Blue Economy and Blue Growth sectors. Innovative approaches were used to scale up the observations taken at local and regional levels to address questions at ocean basin scale. More than 80 research expeditions provided vital new data to help identify the ecosystems most at risk from environmental change in the deep and open ocean, supplemented by data from other diverse sources, including industry and non-scientific sources. Extensive laboratory experiments, data analysis and modelling techniques were used to examine the likely ecosystem impacts of different stressors, such as changes in temperature, oxygen, nutrients and acidity arising from climate change, and from human activities such as deep-sea mining, trawling and pollution.

iAtlantic places capacity building at the core of its mission. Alongside the recruitment of a significant cohort of early career researchers who collectively form the community of iAtlantic Fellows, an extensive capacity building programme was developed to maximise the learning opportunities

provided by the project's work. This programme included hands-on capacity building at sea, instrumentation and technology transfer and training in analytical techniques and data interpretation, as well as introducing aspects of downstream use of research results in ocean management, policy development and governance.

Transfer of knowledge and results to the wider Atlantic stakeholder community and policy makers is an integral part of the iAtlantic approach, implemented through a range of targeted events, open meetings and bilateral discussions, culminating in the largest international symposium yet convened to discuss the implementation of the new UN Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction or 'High Seas' Treaty.

To support informed decision-making and policy development, iAtlantic has made its spatiotemporal data openly available to end-users via the GIS-based GeoNode platform, and all project publications are available via the iAtlantic Zenodo archive:

zenodo.org/communities/iatlantic-project-collection

Sunset over the Mid-Atlantic Ridge during the MoMARSAT2023 cruise. Image courtesy J. Sarrazin/Momarsat 2023

Figure 2: The iAtlantic study areas.

Summary of project results and achievements

Atlantic
oceanography
and ecosystem
connectivity

Ocean circulation is the engine of the Atlantic. It is responsible for the storage and distribution of heat around the ocean, as well as nutrients, oxygen and carbon – all essential for maintaining healthy ecosystems. Ocean circulation is key for the dispersal of pelagic organisms and the larvae of many coastal and deep-sea benthic fauna.

The dynamics of ocean circulation and hydrography are driven by two mechanisms: wind-driven circulation that affects the horizontal movement of water, and the thermohaline, overturning circulation driven by differences in water mass density. In the Atlantic, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC; Fig. 3) is a combination of warm surface water flowing from equatorial regions towards the poles, and cooler, deeper water flowing from the poles towards the equator. In the subpolar and sub-Arctic North Atlantic, the relatively warm water flowing from the equator cools and becomes more saline. As a result, it increases in density, sinks to depth and returns equatorwards and into the other oceans, thus creating the large-scale overturning circulation that plays a key role

in regulating global climate. Global change acts on the AMOC, through warming of surface water and freshening from the atmosphere and from land effects such as melting glaciers. Climate projections consistently show a decline of the AMOC, hence also influencing the capture and storage of carbon in the deep ocean, with consequences of further global warming and for marine ecosystems.

Researchers debate whether the changes in AMOC we see now are the start of a long-term decline or if they are still in the range of natural variability. Despite this, future projections generally agree that AMOC will decline but it remains hard to know what specific implications this will have for Atlantic ecosystems.

Figure 3: Idealised schematic of the overturning circulation in the Atlantic. The schematic represents the pathways of surface (red), intermediate (yellow), deep (blue), and abyssal (purple) waters over the bottom topography (blue shading). Transitions between these colors indicate water mass transformations. Dashed white lines indicate the nominal latitudes of the five Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) monitoring arrays. AC Agulhas Current, ACC Antarctic Circumpolar Current, ARs Agulhas Rings, BC Brazil Current, BCS Benguela Current System, DWBC Deep Western Boundary Current, MC Malvinas Current, NBC North Brazil Current, SEC South Equatorial Current. From Chidichimo et al. (2023).

By the next century, climate change impacts on the AMOC will have affected much of the deep and open Atlantic, altering not only patterns of water temperature and salinity, but also the carbonate chemistry, the distribution of oxygen and the connections between marine communities - which could radically impact marine ecosystems from the bottom of the food chain to top ocean predators. Information from ocean models also advances our understanding of how marine ecosystems are connected. Lagrangian (particle tracking) modelling techniques can be used to determine how drifting organisms (e.g., pelagic larvae, juveniles, marine snow) are dispersed in the Atlantic, and therefore clarify the role that ocean circulation plays in keeping ecosystems connected through the movement of genetic material and food.

Even though modern physical oceanography can enhance ship-based measurements with satellites and autonomous

instruments, the overall picture of Atlantic circulation and hydrography remains patchy, particularly in the deep ocean. The breadth of scales and strong seasonal, interannual and decadal variability of the Atlantic requires long-term monitoring systems and reliable models to fill observation gaps, both geographic and temporal.

iAtlantic's work in measuring and improving understanding of Atlantic Ocean circulation aimed to:

- Align capacities in ocean observations in the North and South Atlantic by improving technical capability in the southern mooring array;
- Determine drivers and explaining spatio/temporal patterns of physical change and variability in ecosystem-relevant parameters and phenomena such as marine heatwaves
- Identify connectivity patterns at regional and basin scales.

Figure 4: Surface currents in the high-resolution atmosphere-ocean model of the ATLAS10 Atlantic Ocean. Image courtesy Tobias Schulzki, GEOMAR.

Activities and outcomes

Ocean hindcasts and forecasts

iAtlantic ran two high-resolution ocean models (INALT20 and VIKING20X) to look back in time at Atlantic Ocean circulation patterns over the past 60 years and to examine changes in the AMOC as response to atmospheric conditions. The model outputs were compared with the present-day observations from oceanographic moorings in the North and South Atlantic.

Coupled ocean-atmosphere models have been developed to better understand future AMOC changes in response to drivers such as changing southern hemisphere wind patterns, and the projected rising concentration of greenhouse gases over the next 50 years. Working with a suite of future climate scenarios (CMIP RCP2.5, RCP 4.5 and RCP8.5) published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC; Masson-Delmott et al., 2021), these model outputs provided the foundational data on future ocean-atmosphere conditions that underpin iAtlantic's research on understanding ecosystem response to environmental change.

iAtlantic has achieved advances in our understanding of interbasin exchange, in particular the phenomenon known as Agulhas leakage (Rühs et al., 2022), where warm, saline water from the Indian Ocean flows into the South Atlantic around the southern tip of Africa, feeding into the southern part of the AMOC. A new finding is that Agulhas leakage did not increase after the mid-1980 but instead stabilised, which has consequences for the AMOC and its stability. Other important advances include the implementation of a new approach that helps to better bridge between ocean and climate models (Fig 4; Schulzki et al., 2022).

Zooming in on specific areas of the Atlantic, ultra-high-resolution ocean models were developed to take a more detailed look at the large-scale circulation changes around specific seafloor features. Examples include the Walvis Ridge in the SE Atlantic for which a 100-m scale model was generated, and the ocean around the Lucky Strike hydrothermal vent on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge which was modelled down to 1-10 m resolution. Outputs from these models demonstrated the impact of small-scale turbulence (such as tides and waves) on the mixing and regional spreading of deep marine organisms.

AMOC monitoring capacity

We studied AMOC variability over recent decades, with particular emphasis on the monthly to multidecadal timescales of natural variability (Biaostoch et al., 2021). iAtlantic improved AMOC monitoring capability by

Figure 5: Deploying the iAtlantic and TRIATLAS moorings in the southwest South Atlantic, December 2022). Image courtesy Michele Baqués.

enhancing the arrays of instruments that currently measure ocean circulation at the northern and southern boundaries of the Atlantic. The array of sensors in the subpolar North Atlantic are part of the OSNAP array, and those at 34.5°S in the South Atlantic comprise the SAMOC/SAMBA array. Analyses in the South Atlantic are particularly concentrated on the western side, providing a multi-year record of the Brazil Current (Chidichimo et al., 2021) and recording the decadal variability in key components of the AMOC. iAtlantic worked in collaboration with the EU-funded TRIATLAS project and the international SAMBA programme to expand the capabilities of this mooring array via the Argentine cruise RV *ARA Austral* in December 2022 (Fig. 5), where two new tall moorings were deployed on the SAMBA line and oxygen sensors added. The iAtlantic mooring measures dissolved oxygen concentrations and fluxes to understand the role of the Brazil Current in the oxygen budget of the subtropical South Atlantic and assess ecosystem changes at the shelf break. A synthesis of existing physical observations made in the South Atlantic over the past 15 years provided new insights into changes in the Southern Hemisphere component of the AMOC, inter-ocean exchanges, water mass pathways, temperature and salinity changes (Chidichimo et al., 2023). The data supplied by the new oxygen sensors will allow analyses from the two AMOC monitoring systems - SAMOC/SAMBA-East in the South Atlantic and the OSNAP array in North Atlantic - to be connected, not only in terms of physical oceanography but also in respect of monitoring ecosystem changes.

In collaboration with University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, iAtlantic worked to better identify water masses and circulation in the South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre, using data collected during three expeditions carried out at 34.5°S, 24°S and 10°W. Subsequent studies focused on ocean current transport in different water layers above the Mid-Atlantic Ridge to estimate AMOC strength, equatorward heat transport and freshwater flux.

Ecosystem connectivity

To better understand the species connectivity of important ecosystem engineering benthic communities in the deep sea (cold-water reefs, mid-Atlantic vent fauna, and seep mussel beds), iAtlantic used population genetics and larval dispersal modelling techniques. Using a combination of genome sequencing of hundreds of individuals for each targeted species, and ocean circulation data from the VIKING ocean model, this analysis shed new light on the directionality and strength of larval exchanges at the scale of the whole Atlantic Ocean.

iAtlantic developed numerous genomic markers for deep-sea vent and seep invertebrates (7 species complexes) and produced genome assemblies for two reef framework-forming cold-water corals (*Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa*, also known as *Desmophyllum pertusum*). This allowed us to perform population genomics analyses in order to define more accurate pathways of population connectivity at transatlantic scale. Coupling larval dispersal modelling with analyses of population genetics showed that seep mussel populations are geographically structured but with some sporadic exchanges of larvae across the Atlantic basin (Portanier et al. 2023). Unlike shrimps, which disperse widely, genetic analyses have shown that hydrothermal gastropods and bivalves are distributed in geographically isolated communities with local areas of hybridisation in between, indicating a strategy of localised dispersal. Conversely, deep corals show fragmentation of populations into discrete reproductive units but with a juxtaposition of genetic lineages in certain places for *Desmophyllum*, suggesting a rather extensive dispersal capacity.

Figure 6: Mussel bed monitored by the TEMPO module on the EMSO-Azores observatory since 2011. Image courtesy Ifremer/Momarsat 2023.

Key results: Atlantic oceanography and ecosystem connectivity

- Improved ocean models have enabled a better understanding of AMOC behaviour in the past, present and future, providing model outputs to underpin iAtlantic research on ecosystem impacts of altered ocean circulation and climate change at a range of scales.
- New capacity to monitor oxygen levels in the South Atlantic and improving ecosystem-relevance of long-term oceanographic monitoring in the North Atlantic.
- Basin-scale ocean and climate models used to research the variability and trends of the AMOC, with particular emphasis on northern vs southern hemisphere impacts. Ultra-high resolution models scaled down the information to underpin ecosystem studies in specific regions, making these useful for ecosystem-level research.
- Made fundamental discoveries in how deep-sea vent species are related across the Atlantic: a new hybrid zone for the gastropod *Peltoispira smaragdina* in the same place as that of hydrothermal mussels indicates that the portion of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge between 26° and 35°N is undoubtedly a zone of least migration - crucial information that must be taken into account in conservation biology.
- Finding hybrids of first/second generation in some populations has validated the hypothesis of long-distance (trans-oceanic) migration in cold seep mussels, even though these events are relatively rare.
- Discovered occurrences of discrete and quite isolated populations in vent gastropods and deep coral species (*Madrepora*) with very limited larval exchanges. This is important for the preservation of vent communities in the face of deep-sea mining, in terms of delimitation of MPAs along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, but also for deep-sea coral reefs facing overfishing by trawling.

Mapping Atlantic ecosystems

To assess deep Atlantic ecosystems we need to begin by understanding what different ecosystems are present, how they are structured and where they occur. However, the Atlantic Ocean is vast and its environmental and biological diversity, spread over a wide range of habitat types, is immense. Obtaining and summarising this information in accessible and intuitive habitat maps was one of the main challenges tackled by iAtlantic's mapping team.

Accurate habitat maps require a huge volume of data in standardised format and resolution. Simply collating this information is an enormous effort in itself as not all seafloor data is available in FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) format. Despite huge data discovery efforts by several initiatives in recent years, many datasets remain in old institutional archives or are privately owned - for example, the massive volume of seafloor survey data held by the oil and gas industry. Once discovered and obtained for use, the data are often in a non-standard format or at a resolution too coarse to be useful for the analyses required. Methodologies for retrieving and dealing with such varied data, blending diverse information to create composite datasets, and then recognising and managing the limitations of those datasets is a major undertaking. Data gaps also present a significant challenge: whilst the physical features of the North Atlantic seafloor are relatively well mapped, there is a scarcity of observational species distribution data - a gap that is even more pronounced in the South Atlantic and particularly in the south-east Atlantic region. New techniques are required to model the available observational data in order to predict what habitats and species might occur in data-poor regions, presenting opportunities for innovation in machine learning and artificial intelligence.

While such an enormous task cannot be completed by a single project in a 4 to 5-year timespan, iAtlantic made significant inroads into these challenges. We set out to map the deep and open-ocean ecosystems of the Atlantic at basin, regional and local scales, specifically to:

- Evaluate and expand our knowledge on ecosystem distribution and the physical environment across the Atlantic;
- Describe the 3D structure of key ecosystems at regional and local scales;
- Identify the main environmental drivers behind ecosystem spatial patterns;
- Develop and apply optimal technologies to enable these mapping activities.

Activities and outcomes

Biodiversity and species distributions are governed by processes at a wide range of spatial and temporal scales, meaning there is no single optimal scale at which ecosystems should or can be studied. We therefore chose to map Atlantic ecosystems at three nested spatial scales (basin, regional and local), so we could better capture different species-environment relationships and understand how those relationships change and influence each other across scales.

Working at basin scale

Our work at the full Atlantic scale started with an extensive data collation and discovery exercise, identifying existing environmental datasets that were not yet published or in the public domain. Here we focused on bathymetry data, the starting point of most habitat maps, and a data type for which many legacy or confidential datasets exist. With only 18% of the Atlantic bathymetry mapped at a fit-for-purpose resolution when iAtlantic began (Wöflf et al., 2019), there was plenty of scope for improvement. Over the course of the project, about 100 legacy datasets were identified and acquired, resulting in 500 Gb of data unlocked and published in the PANGAEA data repository.

Figure 7: Deployment of the ROV Luso during the iMirabilis2 expedition off Cabo Verde, Augst 2021. Image courtesy Murray Roberts.

Atlantic Seabed Areas

- SBA I: Oxic, POC flux influenced, mostly flat with regionally thick sedimented coverage current influenced regions with low seasonal change
- SBA II: MAR spreading centre including abyssal ridges, trenches, seamounts and continental slopes as well as the Gulf of Mexico.
- SBA III: Deep, cold, fresh and oxygen depleted abyssal plain with increased bottom current velocity
- SBA IV: Shallow, warm, nutrient-rich and saline deeper shelf/upper slope zones with thick sediment cover, strong currents and strong local and seasonal changes
- SBA V: Small and regional, cold and fresh deep water influenced areas in North and South Atlantic at medium depth, with locally increased currents and current seasonal change
- SBA VI: Central deep Atlantic cool, nutrient-depleted area with very weak currents, covering some abyssal elevations and sinks
- SBA VII: Small and regional, deep, flat, sedimented oxic region with strong currents and high seasonal current change
- SBA VIII: Wider region around MAR covering new seafloor, faults and fracture zones, with extremely low sediment cover, no currents, very low oxygen and temperature
- SBA IX: Nutrient-rich, fresh, warm water continental shelf regions with thick sediment cover and strong seasonal fluctuations

Ref. Ellipsoid: WGS 84;

Figure 8: Map of Atlantic seabed areas. From Schumacher et al. 2022.

Figure 9: Rockfish and Cerianthid anemones in the Whittard Canyon, NE Atlantic. Image courtesy NOC/JC237.

A major contribution came from Petrobras in Brazil, who provided 200,000 km² of their survey data to the project. Overall, this exercise resulted in the addition of 571,634km² of bathymetry data from the Atlantic being added to the global, publicly accessible record. New bathymetry data were also collected during iAtlantic field campaigns and associated expeditions, leading to a total more than 1 million km² of 'new' data made freely available by iAtlantic.

Beyond collating these data, we demonstrated their importance through two basin-wide activities: analysing Atlantic landscapes and habitat suitability modelling.

iAtlantic used advanced clustering and machine-learning algorithms to identify nine different seabed environments across the Atlantic Ocean. These were differentiated by their geological, geomorphological and/or bottom water characteristics, extracted from publicly available datasets on bathymetry, sediment type, oceanography, hydrodynamics and primary productivity. The nine objectively defined seabed types represent the main marine landscapes in the Atlantic, and the resulting map (Fig. 8) enables areas of high landscape diversity to be identified, which may correspond to locations of high biodiversity, and could inform target areas for conservation or further research.

Habitat suitability modelling of 17 taxa of either conservation or commercial interest was carried out, including vulnerable marine ecosystem (VME) indicator taxa such as cold-water corals, sea pens and sharks, but also commercially important deep-water shrimp and fish. We used ensemble models to predict suitable habitat distributions under present-day and future [2081-2100] conditions. Models were based on publicly available basin-wide environmental variables, and future climate scenarios used by the IPCC (CMIP RCP2.5, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5). Taxa presence records were compiled

from OBIS, the NOAA Deep-Sea Coral Data Portal, the ICES VME data portal, and project partners' observational databases. The modelled VME indicator and commercial taxa distributions show a decrease in predicted suitable habitat in the future, the trend being most pronounced under higher emission scenarios. Mirroring trends from our ecosystem time-series assessments described later in this report (p18), the modelled deep-sea fish, sharks, shrimps and sea pen distributions are predicted to shift towards higher latitudes under higher emission scenarios, while most cold-water corals are predicted to shift towards lower latitudes.

Regional scale (100-1000 km² extent)

Most of iAtlantic's mapping activity was carried out at the regional scale, ranging from new data acquisition with the latest technologies, to focused habitat suitability modelling and region-wide mapping efforts.

EUNIS-classified habitat maps were created for each of the 12 iAtlantic study areas, either making improvements to existing EUNIS habitat maps, translating (or 'cross-walking') other regional habitat classification schemes, or developing new maps based on depth and substratum information from partners' or public databases. While the results enabled a certain amount of cross-region comparison, they also illustrated the large differences in data availability and quality between regions. All habitat maps, together with their associated confidence maps, are available in the iAtlantic GeoNode portal (see p34).

Habitat suitability models were developed in eight of the iAtlantic study areas, using the same ensemble modelling approach as applied at the basin scale. Choices of taxa, model resolution and environmental predictors were driven by regional requirements in terms of conservation and/or management needs and data availability. When comparing model outputs, including estimated species-environment relationships, it is clear that species distributions at the regional scale are typically driven by water mass properties and by proxies for food supply, represented either by terrain parameters, hydrodynamic variables or direct estimates of primary productivity reaching the species in question. Novel metrics describing these environmental conditions, such as kinetic energy dissipation, consecutive disparity index of seasonal water column characteristics, or a new water chemistry index, were developed in iAtlantic and found to be significant predictors.

In the basin-wide habitat suitability modelling, large regional differences existed in data availability, particularly of species presence records. This was especially critical in the south-eastern sector of iAtlantic's interest (e.g.,

Figure 10 (above): An example of a species distribution model. Predictive habitat maps for the cold-water coral *A. arbuscula* at each seamount in Cabo Verde. From iAtlantic Deliverable 2.5.

Figure 11 (below): Deploying the AUV Autosub6000 off Cabo Verde during the iMirabilis2 expedition, August 2021. Image courtesy Murray Roberts.

Cabo Verde, and Walvis Ridge). Innovative approaches to deal with such limited datasets were tested, including down-sampling methods of pseudo-absence points to counteract the class imbalance or training the models on well-sampled seamounts in order to apply the species-environment relationships to less sampled locations in the same archipelago (Cabo Verde).

Local scale (100-1000 m² extent)

At selected sites in iAtlantic study areas (e.g., some submarine canyons, cold-water coral reefs, hydrothermal vents and volcanic island flanks) ultra-high resolution, 3D habitat maps were developed, using new approaches such as Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry and ROV-based acoustic mapping of vertical terrain. This allowed us to quantify the structural complexity of the habitat, a parameter which was shown to significantly influence benthic community composition and fine-scale habitat distribution (Price et al., 2019; Van Audenhaege et al., 2022). The 3D models captured terrain and environmental

information that is lost in traditional 2D approaches, which can be picked up by machine-learning algorithms for habitat classification (de Oliveira et al., 2021; Van Audenhaege et al., 2021). In addition, the 3D reconstructions became excellent material for outreach activities such as virtual reality simulations.

Figure 12: French Prime Minister Jean Castex experiences a virtual dive on the Eiffel Tower edifice, February 2021. Image © Ifremer / Stephane Lesbats.

Key results: Mapping Atlantic ecosystems

- 571,634 km² of Atlantic bathymetry data were added to the global, publicly accessible record.
- Basin-wide classification of seabed types defined nine different seabed environments across the Atlantic Ocean, which potentially correspond to locations of high biodiversity and could inform target areas for conservation or further research.
- Habitat suitability models for 17 taxa were developed, presenting present-day distributions and future predictions (2081-2100) under three climate change scenarios. VME indicator and commercial taxa distributions show a decrease in predicted suitable habitat in the future. The modelled deep-sea fish, shark, shrimp and sea pens are predicted to shift towards higher latitudes, while most cold-water corals are predicted to shift towards lower latitudes.
- Regional habitat suitability models developed in 8 iAtlantic study areas for species of conservation and commercial interest. Species distributions at regional scale (100-1000 km² extent) are typically driven by water mass properties and by proxies for food supply.
- Habitat structural complexity quantified at the local scale (10-100 m²) using ROV- and AUV-based high-resolution mapping and Structure-for-Motion photogrammetry.
- New metrics proposed for quantifying environmental variability that improve predictive power of habitat suitability models, and that provide ecological insights in niche requirements of species of interest.
- New insights in sub-metre 3D structure of key deep-water habitats, and how this structure influences local species diversity and distribution.
- Machine learning approaches developed for creating habitat maps, at scales ranging from the entire Atlantic basin to local, high-resolution surveys.

Drivers of ecosystem change and tipping points

In today's ocean, ecosystems are subject to stresses from multiple sources, including environmental change because of natural variations or cycles, climate change, and increasing levels of human activities in the ocean. Regions experiencing faster and larger changes over the next century are more likely to undergo ecosystem shifts and reach tipping points, leading to permanent changes in structure, functioning and/or provision of the ecosystem services essential to human well-being.

iAtlantic undertook significant research into understanding the drivers of ecosystem change in the ocean as part of our integrated assessment of ecosystem status and dynamics. We examined historical patterns of ecosystem change to identify, understand and quantify its drivers and tipping points, and then assess place-based risks in each of the 12 iAtlantic study areas over the last 50 years.

Using a place-based approach, this work aimed to:

- Identify the nature of ecosystem changes and test for gradual or abrupt shifts, and quantify system-specific thresholds;
- Assess the single and cumulative effects of oceanographic variability (and any anthropogenic pressures) on key ecosystem compartments;
- Score each of the iAtlantic study areas according to whether their focal ecosystems are likely to change under future climate change forecasts.

Added to the lack of robust, long-term observations of marine species and ecosystems in the deep sea and open ocean, noisy data, incomplete data, effects of larger-scale oceanographic regime shifts and potentially confounding variables challenged this work. Despite the challenges, our approach resolved interannual to multidecadal changes in ecosystem compartments in all study areas, identified statistical breakpoints that are potential tipping points, and helped constrain many of the drivers related to these changes. While all the analyses come with caveats, iAtlantic's place-based approach gives managers and spatial planning authorities a better understanding of ecosystem variability and vulnerability, provides insights into alternative states or trajectories of ecosystems in each study area as well as possible drivers that could push or tip ecosystems into a new state.

Activities and outcomes

iAtlantic's effort to improve the understanding of ecosystem stability, vulnerability and tipping points in each of the 12 study areas over the last 50 years was guided by methodological standardisation but allowed for flexibility so that region-specific drivers of change could be tailored to fit analyses. Methods to collect and reconstruct iAtlantic time series were as diverse as the study areas, species and ecosystems studied.

We are extremely grateful to the many collaborators, institutes, governments and authorities for permission to make use of the facilities, the data and the many experts who advised analysts along the way. Data from marine observatories were fundamental for this work, including from the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO), the Cape Verde Ocean Observatory (CVOO) and the Bermuda Atlantic Time-Series (BATS). Long-term monitoring programmes and surveys of zooplankton, cetaceans and groundfish off study areas like Nova Scotia in eastern Canada, and the North Atlantic Sightings Surveys (NASS) off Iceland were key, as was local ecological knowledge of humpback whales in the Sargasso Sea. Fisheries-dependent data were also crucial, particularly in our South Atlantic study areas. Alongside classical survey and monitoring methods, alternative approaches

Figure 13: Capelin from Icelandic waters. Courtesy S. Egilsdottir, MFRI

Figure 14: Temporal extent of iAtlantic time series and biological components studied (*excluding capelin larvae). From iAtlantic Deliverable 3.1.

such as Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry for 3D reconstruction of geological features, capture-recapture modelling from whale fluke photos, the use of acoustic Doppler conductivity profilers (ADCPs) as a proxy of zooplankton abundance, and palaeoceanographic and geochemical proxies of ecosystem change over centuries to millennia were all used to reconstruct time series.

A Master Time Series Database was developed, offering a new compilation of ecosystem time series spanning the full Atlantic Ocean and a range of marine taxa including prokaryotes and eukaryotes across the size spectrum. These include data and samples from marine observatories and repeated surveys/sampling, commercial fisheries, government and scientific projects and programmes, geochemical proxies from archived museum and scientific samples of corals and sediment cores, hydroacoustics equipment, ancient DNA, capture-recapture and local ecological knowledge.

Through this flexible place-based approach, several themes emerged about ecosystem change over the last 50 years.

#1: Abrupt ecosystem changes, late 1990s to early 2000s

We discovered statistical ‘breakpoints’ in our datasets that suggest abrupt shifts occurred in many study areas, especially around the late 1990s and early 2000s. Breakpoints are strong, significant and steep changes in

species or ecosystems and could represent tipping points if the ecosystem can no longer cope with environmental change. A major change in all regions between 1995 and 2004 coincided with a decrease in the AMOC which led to regional and local oceanographic changes. Identifying the drivers of change in each region highlighted how oceanographic variability can alter the ecosystem at a larger scale, impacting ecosystem health by modifying ecological interactions from primary production and prey availability, and propagating all the way up the food chain. The relative and cumulative impact of multiple stressors, including climate change, fishing, and deep-sea mining, warrants further investigation to describe the underlying biological mechanisms.

#2: Tropicalisation of marine fauna and relationships with sea temperature

Relationships with sea temperature were by far the most common trend reported across the 12 study areas: shifts in phytoplankton, zooplankton and fish communities associated with an increase in warm-water species, changes in the average lengths of commercial species, shifts in spawning and nursing grounds, and large spatio-temporal variations in whale sightings. Northward expansion of monkfish range and capelin spawning habitat around Iceland were both associated with warmer waters. Long-term ocean warming heralds today’s new era of widespread

species 'tropicalisation'. Zooplankton species with warm water affinities now characterise the community off the deep and open ocean over the Scotian Slope. Widespread declines in catches of cooler water species of groundfish like Argentine hake, Argentine croaker and codling occurred on the Brazilian meridional margin (Perez & Sant'Ana, 2022). Catches of cooler-water species of large migratory pelagic fish such as albacore and Atlantic bluefin tuna have also significantly declined across Brazil, the Malvinas Current, Romanche Fracture Zone, Angola to the Congo Lobe and from Walvis Ridge to South Africa, seemingly related to positive thermal anomalies in these regions.

#3: Human activities and marine management are intertwined with trends

The tropicalisation trends identified by iAtlantic are all strongly related to thermal regimes, but the effects of fisheries pressure itself could not be entirely discounted.

Nor could the effect of the International Whaling Commission (IWC) ban on commercial whaling in 1986, and marine protected area (MPA) designations. Re-analysis of beaked whale sightings recorded in the Gully MPA off eastern Canada show increases over time, which Whitehead (2013) suggest could in part relate to decreases in noise after the MPA was designated in 2004. For pilot whale, striped dolphin and white-sided dolphin, a combination of shifts in overall population size, habitat suitability and anthropogenic activity levels are also likely drivers of change (Whitehead, 2020). In the Sargasso Sea, iAtlantic scientists re-constructed humpback whale abundance and discovered whales have been steadily increasing since 2012 (Fig. 16). Although some of these changes might relate to progressive increases in primary production recorded by Bermuda Atlantic Time-Series Study (BATS), these increases are very much intertwined with larger scale population recovery post-whaling.

Figure 15: A) Reconstructing time series using structure-from-motion photogrammetry on hydrothermal vents (image M.Matabos); B) capture-recapture modelling from whale fluke identification (image A.Stevenson); C) trialling the use of ADCPs to reconstruct inter-annual changes in mesoplankton (image H.Hauss); D) reconstructing ecosystem changes from cold-water corals over decades (image C.Millo) and E) over millennia (image D.Hebbeln).

Figure 16: Time series were reconstructed from boat-based humpback whale sightings since 2011 around Bermuda, where the waters are increasingly busy with marine wildlife tourism, sport fishing, shipping and renewable energy. Image courtesy Andrew Stevenson.

At the Lucky Strike hydrothermal vent on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, time-series analyses highlighted high stability in both the vent fauna and microbes and environmental conditions. This is strong evidence that these climax communities are highly preserved and not used to experiencing disturbances, suggesting low ecosystem resilience to any disturbance. The

exploitation of hydrothermal vents like Lucky Strike (e.g., for mineral extraction) could therefore have deleterious long-term or even irreversible impacts on these communities and the ecosystem they support, including peripheral abyssal fauna that rely on chemosynthetic production.

Key results: Drivers of ecosystem change and tipping points

- iAtlantic analysed various living ecosystem 'compartments' ranging from datasets on bacteria and primary producers to vulnerable marine ecosystem (VME) indicator taxa, whales, swordfish and sharks, of great conservation interest and value to the Atlantic socioeconomy.
- Drivers of temporal change were analysed across a suite of deep-sea and open-ocean time series datasets. Relationships with sea temperature were by far the most common trend.
- Statistical breakpoints reveal large temporal shifts and potential tipping points, particularly around the late 1990s and early 2000s, coincident with larger-scale oceanographic trends from the surface of the open ocean to the abyss. Many study areas showed breakpoints or declines in commercially important species (e.g., Atlantic halibut, monkfish, albacore and bluefin tuna).
- A tropicalisation trend of warm-water affinity species becoming more abundant was observed across the Atlantic from Eastern Canada to the Malvinas current, and from the subpolar north Atlantic to south Brazil and Africa. While temperature seems strongly related to these changes, effects of other pressures such as fisheries cannot be ruled out.
- Steady increases in species important for marine wildlife tourism (e.g., humpback whales) were also noted and likely related to larger scale population recovery trends post-whaling.
- Over millennial timescales, tipping points in South Atlantic cold-water coral ecosystems coincided with AMOC-driven changes to hydrodynamics and food supply, just like in the North Atlantic. However, anomalous ocean circulation changes over the last century significantly impacted the deep-sea benthos in the North Atlantic, with changes in surface ocean frontal activity altering food supply to the seafloor.
- Methodological and statistical approaches proposed by iAtlantic can be applied to many additional existing samples and time-series in the Atlantic, thus laying important groundwork for future large-scale ecosystem assessment.

Impact of multiple stressors on Atlantic ecosystems

The deep ocean is increasingly under threat from multiple sources. Fishing is targeting deeper parts of the ocean, and potential future deep-sea mining brings a new set of impacts that could significantly affect Atlantic ecosystem health. Human exploitation of ocean resources is happening in parallel with climate change, which is generating additional stresses in the form of ocean warming, acidification, and – in some regions – reduced oxygen levels and restricted food supply.

iAtlantic set out to understand the cumulative impacts of climate change and human activities on key deep-sea organisms, including pelagic taxa, soft-sediment and hard-substrate benthic organisms, in order to understand and predict how and where multiple stressors could drastically impact ecosystem functions and services. A multidisciplinary approach using autonomous *in situ* instruments, field sampling, food web modelling and lab experiments provided new information, particularly in areas of the Atlantic where existing data coverage is poor. We used productivity and water-mass gradients that naturally exist in the Atlantic to examine how deep-sea benthic assemblages respond to changes in environmental variables such as productivity and particulate organic carbon (POC) flux. Specifically, we aimed to:

- Expand our knowledge on the baseline functioning of deep-sea pelagic and benthic ecosystems
- Assess the effects of different environmental stressors on deep-sea pelagic and benthic organisms
- Assess the effects of different environmental stressors on the larvae of habitat-forming organisms.

Activities and outcomes

The iMirabilis2 flagship expedition in July-August 2021 provided the opportunity to study benthic and demersal ecosystems using different types of landers and multi-stressor experiments, and to examine how ecosystem processes and functioning vary across different natural environmental settings in the north and south Atlantic.

Several *in situ* experiments were completed to assess how deep-sea ecosystems might be impacted by changing food supply, quality and composition. For example, since deoxygenation and overfishing in the equatorial Atlantic will probably cause a shift from fish (mackerel) to squid-dominated ecosystems, we ran an experiment to examine the implications for abyssal scavengers that rely on food fall from the surface ocean. iAtlantic used a benthic camera lander deployed to 4,200m depth with different fish and squid baits (Fig.17). A clear difference in the biodiversity of scavengers and feeding activity at the squid and fish baits was observed, with the squid being very rapidly consumed compared to the fish bait. The rapid removal of squid was likely related to the smaller size and softer tissue compared

to the oily mackerel since more energy would be needed by the scavenger species to eat the more rigid flesh of the fish bait. Compared to other sites, we found that both squid and fish consumption rates were faster than at shallower depths in the more eutrophic (high nutrient, low oxygen) Arctic Ocean and the southern Norwegian Sea, which could indicate that declining productivity may lead to more intense scavenging activity at the seafloor. This would then likely advantage faster-swimming fauna, which was also a key reason for the different community composition observed between the fish and squid baits. Ultimately, these experiments showed how changes to upper ocean ecosystems may have impacts thousands of metres below the ocean surface, and demonstrate the close connection between food input and deep-sea ecosystem processes.

Figure 17: Scavengers attack mackerel bait on the baited camera lander at 4200 m water depth offshore Cabo Verde, August 2021. Image courtesy A.Sweetman/Lyell Centre-HWU/ iMirabilis2.

iAtlantic examined how changing food supply rates might alter benthic ecosystems at abyssal depths in the Atlantic. These studies compared seafloor processes and ecosystem functioning in the eutrophic Porcupine Abyssal Plain (PAP) to the more mesotrophic Cabo Verde Abyssal Basin (CVAB) using modelled data alongside *in situ* data gathered with a benthic chamber lander (Fig. 18). Both datasets revealed that the abyssal CVAB functions as a mesotrophic abyssal habitat characterised by lower bacterial biomass but greater carbon processing efficiency compared to the

Figure 18: Taking water samples from the benthic chamber lander during iMirabilis2. Image courtesy Murray Roberts.

PAP. From this we can conclude that as food supply to the seafloor decreases with climate change, differences in food-web organisation and energy flows could force abyssal ecosystems to use carbon more efficiently.

Impacts of deep-sea mining

Deep-sea mining is considered one of the most pressing future human threats to deep-sea ecosystems. Mining operations will produce sediment plumes that can disperse over vast areas of the ocean, affecting both pelagic and benthic realms. However, the extent and nature of ecosystem impacts resulting from these plumes remains unclear. Climate change presents an additional overarching stress to deep-sea ecosystems that may be impacted by mining activities. To investigate this, iAtlantic conducted a series of studies to determine the nature of mining and climate change impacts on pelagic fauna such as jellyfish, and seafloor engineers such as cold-water corals.

The effects of climate change in the deep sea will first be felt by organisms in the water column. To study how these animals might be affected by climate change and non-toxic sediment plumes produced by manganese nodule mining, a variety of pelagic fauna were exposed to varying levels of warming (*in situ*, +2°C, +4°C for 7-9 hours) and abyssal sediment suspension concentrations (0, 16.7, 33.3, 166.7,

333.3 mg·L⁻¹ for 24 hours) in the laboratory. Both behavioural (posture, mucus sloughing) and physiological responses were measured, including respiration, ammonium excretion rates and gene expression. The deep-sea jellyfish *Periphylla periphylla* increased its metabolic activity in response to warming and sediment plume exposure.

An increase of 4°C resulted in the metabolic rate of the jellyfish increasing to twice the rate observed at normal ocean temperatures. Exposure to sediment had a strong physical and metabolic effect on the jellyfish, including production of excess mucus (Fig. 19) and increased respiration. The most concentrated sediment treatment resulted in a respiration increase similar to that induced by the most extreme temperature treatment of +4°C. The increase in metabolic rates observed in the sediment experiments will impact the energetics and demand for food in this deep-sea jellyfish, which is adapted to a slow metabolic pace in an environment with scarce food sources.

iAtlantic also investigated the nature of the impacts of toxic sediment plumes expected from mining of seafloor massive sulphide deposits from an inactive hydrothermal vent field in the Azores. We performed a series of aquarium experiments to test the effects of different concentrations of suspended polymetallic sulphide (PMS) particles generated during potential mining on different cold-water coral taxa (scleractinian hard corals, gorgonians, black corals) and vent organisms (mussels, gastropods and a commensal worm).

Figure 19: Mucus sloughing off a deep-sea jellyfish when exposed to a simulated mining plume. Image courtesy H. Hauss.

Experimental results from the cold-water corals show that relatively low concentrations of PMS particles can impair their physiology, most likely from combined and potentially synergistic mechanical and toxicological effects, ultimately resulting in coral death within a short period (Fig. 20; Carreiro-Silva et al. 2022). Black corals were particularly sensitive to PMS, with death coming after only 24-hour exposure to 10 mg.L⁻¹. Gorgonians were able to survive for 14-27 days when exposed to low concentrations of 2 mg.L⁻¹ but died within 4 days when exposed to 10 and 50 mg.L⁻¹. Of great concern is the acute sensitivity of *L. pertusa* (*D. pertusum*) larvae to low concentrations (2.5-5 mg.L⁻¹), which resulted in death after only 24 hours' exposure.

The cumulative effects of ocean acidification and reduced food supply (as predicted in future ocean-climate scenarios) and PMS particles was studied for the hard coral *Desmopyllum dianthus*. The coral was first exposed to climate change conditions for 3 months to give time for the coral to adjust to the changed environmental conditions, followed by a 1-month exposure to PMS particles. We observed an overriding response to PMS particles with all corals dying after 28 days' exposure, irrespective of the climate scenario. However, corals subjected to reduced food availability were the first to present signs of metabolic depression and death, indicating the importance of projected decreases in food delivered from the surface to the deep ocean for corals coping with other stressors. Experiments with benthic vent fauna tested single and combined effects of deoxygenation and PMS particles. Results showed that vent fauna were not affected by deoxygenation, but exposure to PMS (420 mg.L⁻¹) caused physiological stress on the vent mussel *Bathymodiulus azoricus* and death of the commensal polychaete worm *Branchiopolinoe seepensis*, but did not affect the gastropod mollusc *Protolira valvatoides*. These studies produced important data that can inform the development of the International Seabed Authority's standards and guidelines for deep-sea mining.

Climate change impacts on larvae

Studying the single and cumulative impacts of climate change on the larvae of key deep-sea benthic species has been an important part of iAtlantic's work. Larval stages constitute the only pelagic phase of benthic organisms, ensuring dispersal and connectivity among populations and ultimately the survival of the species. A series of laboratory experiments tested the impacts of climate change (ocean warming, acidification) and human activities (sedimentation arising from trawling, deep-sea mining, microplastics) on embryonic and larval survival, development and swimming ability of gorgonians, scleractinians and black corals. Results suggest some resilience to acidification, natural sediments

Figure 20: The coral *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor* after 3 days of exposure to the different treatments: (A) control, (B) quartz particles, and (C) PMS particles. Images reproduced with permission from Carreiro-Silva et al. (2022).

and microplastics but acute sensitivity to deep-sea mining as described above.

Ocean temperature was shown to play a particularly important role on the larval stages of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa*. This reef-building species has a near-global but scattered distribution and is found in waters with temperatures ranging 4-13°C. Because of their wide distribution across latitudes and water temperatures, the

embryonic and larval development rate, as well as larval swimming speed, is expected to vary strongly among populations. Increased seawater temperature due to ocean warming will also affect these larval properties. To test the effects of ocean warming, newly fertilised embryos and very young larvae were exposed to targeted water temperatures of 4, 8, 12, 16 and 20°C. Results showed increased larval development rate and swimming speed with increasing seawater temperature. This means that these larvae are likely to survive under future increased temperature but will not travel as far before they are mature enough to settle, which will likely affect connectivity among populations. Mathematical equations describing the relationship between temperature and embryo/larvae development and larval swimming speed can now be used in biophysical larval dispersal models for more accurate predictions of larval dispersal in various geographical locations and future climate change scenarios.

iAtlantic conducted the first long-term (>9 months) multi-stressor experiment to test the interaction between projected changes in ocean temperature, carbonate chemistry and dissolved oxygen concentrations on the cold-water corals *Lophelia pertusa* (*Desmophyllum pertusum*) and *Dendrophyllia cornigera*. Results show that while *L. pertusa* growth rates may be negatively affected by ocean chemistry changes driven by the dissolution and coralporosis of dead material, *D. cornigera* revealed high plasticity and resilience to climate change stressors. These results highlight that while some coral species may be able to survive ocean acidification, significant changes may be expected in terms of net habitat loss in locations where ocean acidification is most pronounced, leading to a net loss of coral ecosystem functioning, habitat provisioning and potential carbon turnover.

Key results: Impacts of multiple stressors

- Baited camera work using fish and squid baits shows how changes to upper ocean ecosystems from climate change (i.e., increase in squid biomass) and overfishing (i.e., reduction of fish biomass), may cause effects thousands of metres below the ocean surface and the close connection between food input and deep-sea ecosystem processes.
- iAtlantic collected new data on the baseline ecosystem functioning of the mesotrophic Cabo Verde Abyssal Plain in the South Atlantic. Comparisons with the ecosystem functioning in the more eutrophic Porcupine Abyssal Plain (PAP) in the North Atlantic gave insights on how changing food supply rates may alter benthic ecosystems at abyssal depths in the Atlantic.
- *Ex situ* experiments conducted using isotopic tracers and sediments from the continental slope of Cabo Verde Basin suggested that increased temperature and decreased food quality predicted for the end of the century would decrease the carbon storage capacity of the deep seafloor.
- We investigated the impacts of sediment plumes potentially generated during deep-sea mining activities, alone and in combination with climate change effects, on pelagic fauna, cold-water corals and vent organisms. These experiments provided new evidence and data on the important negative impacts that can be expected from deep-sea mining operations.
- Laboratory experiments assessed the potential impacts of climate change and human pressures on early life stages of cold-water corals, providing important data that can help us predict consequences of multiple stressors on the dispersal and connectivity of coral populations in the Atlantic.
- iAtlantic's long-term (>9 months) multi-stressor experiment on the cold-water corals *Lophelia pertusa* and *Dendrophyllia cornigera* showed that while some coral species may be able to survive the effects of ocean acidification, significant changes may be expected in terms of net habitat loss and consequent net loss of coral ecosystem functioning, habitat provisioning and potential carbon turnover.

Spatial and temporal management and protection

Climate change and human activities cause an array of impacts on all marine ecosystems. In response, management solutions need to be tailored to suit individual situations and scenarios. In many circumstances it may be necessary to balance the mitigation of biodiversity risks with socio-economic needs and devise sustainable ways to manage and use marine resources. Improving management of ocean space has been the primary approach used globally to address these challenges.

Area-based management refers to the integrated, sustainable, cross-sectoral management of human activities in a spatially defined area. Examples of area-based management tools (ABMT) for the ocean include marine spatial planning (MSP), marine protected areas (MPAs), ecological networks, dynamic management measures, and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs) including indigenous-, community- and privately managed areas. ABMTs also include sectoral tools, such as closure of certain vulnerable areas to fishing, shipping or mining.

iAtlantic aimed to provide the necessary relevant information and tools to support competent authorities in the development and use of integrated, sustainable management decisions and practices at appropriate scales. To achieve this, iAtlantic worked towards the following objectives:

- Compile spatial and temporal information to produce a series of outputs illustrating the current and future projected changes in status of Atlantic ecosystems throughout the Atlantic;
- Apply site prioritisation techniques to identify zones where different management regimes can be applied;
- Generate planning scenarios to inform marine spatial planning and sustainable development in the Atlantic.

Activities and outcomes

To produce transparent ocean basin-scale management scenarios for the whole Atlantic, iAtlantic developed and agreed a set of principles, goals and objectives to guide its systematic conservation planning (SCP) prioritisation approach and scenario development. We compiled an overview of existing sustainable management and conservation objectives reflected in political commitments, declarations and legal obligations related to the Atlantic marine environment, from which we developed a list of potential SCP goals and objectives. This then informed discussions on the SCP goals and objectives and provided the basis for consultation with stakeholder groups, recognising that both the CBD Global Biodiversity Framework and the UN BBNJ treaty will both provide an impetus and mechanism for ABMT in ABNJ and national waters.

iAtlantic used spatiotemporal data streams and spatial numerical tools to produce a range of optimisation scenarios that integrated species distributions, habitat data, environmental information and human stressor data, including climate change. Within each scenario we identified priority areas in the Atlantic Ocean better suited to address relevant management goals and objectives and to inform planning discussions by management organisations. The scenarios provided practical examples to evaluate how assumptions affect potential spatial planning of large-scale marine systems under a range of conditions. In this regard, iAtlantic generated several scenarios of priority areas for management and conservation, and of areas for restoration under present-day environmental conditions. The results were strongly driven by the management goals and objectives and suggested a need for dialogue between different stakeholders to develop feasible and effective conservation planning. The results also suggested that the implementation of a restoration agenda implies higher cost when compared to the conservation plan due to the inclusion of areas of higher human use. Ocean basin-scale management strategies that consider transboundary aspects, such as the cooperation between different nations, appear to improve conservation planning effectiveness, achieving conservation targets with a lower area and at a lower cost.

Figure 21: A deep-sea shark swims through a coral garden in the Azores. Image courtesy IMAR/U.Azores.

Figure 22: The Regional Government of the Azores used a simplified and complemented network of priority areas developed by iAtlantic in the stakeholder discussions and negotiations. The final configuration of the revised and expanded network of marine protected areas in the Azores to achieve the 30% protection target is now undergoing a public consultancy process.

We evaluated how different methodologies to address climate change affect the range of scenario solutions. We noticed that methodologies that consider climate metrics or future habitat suitability produce different solutions, highlighting the need to clearly define what the climate-related conservation goals aim to achieve through spatial planning. Similarly, we found that different methodologies to address the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to protect 30% of its seas including 10% under strict protection affect spatial planning solutions. Despite the scarcity of data in many areas of the Atlantic Ocean, we showed how existing data on deep-sea biodiversity and geomorphology can inform area-based management in the deep Atlantic in a transparent, reproducible and rigorous way.

Regional spatial planning: The Azores

iAtlantic also informed conservation and sustainable management of deep-sea ecosystems at regional scales. In the Azores, for example, iAtlantic finalised the development of management scenarios to inform the selection of priority areas to achieve well-defined management and conservation goals and objectives in the deep-sea

portion of the Azores Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). The Regional Government of the Azores used a simplified and complementary network of priority areas developed by iAtlantic in their stakeholder discussions and negotiations. The final configuration of the revised and expanded network of marine protected areas in the Azores to achieve the CBD's 30% protection target (Fig. 22), is now undergoing public consultation. Systematic conservation planning for the deep-water of the Azores suggested the prioritisation outputs are highly dependent on the goals and objectives adopted. It also highlighted that the prioritisation outputs, as well as the performance assessment and the forecast impact of management measures, depend on the range of conservation features, representation targets, cost model, boundary penalties and constraints considered. The overarching conclusion of the forecast ecosystem outcomes is that networks of MPAs can have strong positive effects on the biomass of top predators, leading to spatial trophic cascade effects through the food web. Model projections also suggest that the implementation of 'no-take areas' should be accompanied by other fisheries management measures to avoid detriment to commercially important

Figure 23: Participants at one of the systematic conservation planning stakeholder workshops in South Africa. Image courtesy Kerry Sink.

fisheries stocks from displacement of fishing effort. Indeed, complementing fisheries closures with additional fisheries management measures (e.g., fishing effort reductions) may be crucial to fully achieving ecosystem-based management goals.

Regional spatial planning: South Africa

iAtlantic supported new research to advance spatial planning and prioritisation to guide future marine protected area (MPA) expansion efforts in South Africa. This work linked with other local projects being conducted in South Africa and built on previous prioritisations, including the Offshore MPA project and the National Coastal and Marine Spatial Biodiversity Plan. It aimed to support the Operation Phakisa Oceans Economy target of identifying a further 5% area that could advance protection of the marine area

around mainland South Africa from 5.4% to 10%, which is also in line with the medium-term target of the National Protected Area Expansion Strategy.

Four stakeholder workshops (Fig. 23) were held to support the introduction of the plan, review planning inputs and approaches, distil key lessons from previous MPA expansion efforts and to help support further project design, planning and fund raising for more participatory efforts to support MPA expansion. Involving stakeholders from academia, conservation, commercial fisheries, small-scale fisheries, environmental consulting, mining, government, shipping, and the petroleum industry, there was overall support for a science-based SCP approach and requests for increased clarity in terms of definitions, as well as co-ordination of efforts to support MPA expansion.

The planning framework included more than 1,000 data layers spanning benthic and pelagic ecosystem types, species (such as turtles, sharks, seabirds and Vulnerable marine indicator taxa), ecological processes and unique and special features including VMEs and potential VME features. The plan prioritised protection in areas of more stable climate outlooks, with further work needed to assess for climate resilience and connectivity. The plan also seeks to align with other prioritisations and initiatives including transboundary measures and projects. Stakeholders appreciated the comprehensive nature of the planning framework and key lessons emerged in terms of participation of rights holders, knowledge holders and other stakeholders. Outputs from this work will inform the design of the expansion of South Africa's existing network of MPAs to help achieve a 10% protection target, as well as supporting further efforts towards the 30x30 CBD Global Biodiversity Framework targets.

Figure 24: Training the next generation of marine scientists is an important component of ocean conservation strategies in South Africa. Image courtesy Isabelle Ansoorge / Eleonora Puccinelli / SEAmester programme.

Key results: Spatial and temporal management and protection

- iAtlantic demonstrated that improved deep-sea biodiversity assessments and regional management scenarios can inform the conservation and sustainable management of ecosystems in the Atlantic.
- We produced transparent ocean basin-scale management scenarios for the whole Atlantic that considered the sustainable management and conservation objectives reflected in political commitments, declarations and legal obligations related to the Atlantic marine environment.
- Our results informed conservation and sustainable management of deep-sea ecosystems at regional scales. Improved deep-sea biodiversity assessments and regional management scenarios were used by the Regional Government of the Azores in the stakeholder discussions and public consultancy and included in the final design of the expansion of the existing network of Marine Protected Areas to achieve the 30% protection target.
- South Africa currently protects 5.4% of its mainland marine territory. iAtlantic's results can inform the design of the expansion of the existing network of Marine Protected Areas to achieve a 10% protection target. In addition, the plan provides a basis for supporting further work towards the 30x30 CBD Global Biodiversity Framework targets and will improved deep-sea biodiversity assessments and management, including for sensitive seabed habitats.
- To support iAtlantic's systematic conservation planning work, a GIS-based GeoNode platform was developed (see p34) that allows users to search for, visualise, download and share 386 (and counting) geospatial datasets. These include pre-existing geospatial datasets relevant to iAtlantic research as well as new research outputs produced by the project.

Figure 25: Cold-water corals and associated fauna offshore South Africa. Image courtesy African Coelacanth Ecosystem Programme (ACEP)

Managing and visualising data

In line with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot, iAtlantic's Data Management Plan and Data Policy were designed to provide the consortium with a state-of-the-art data handling workflow in accordance with the FAIR principles (ensuring data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable). Supported by data management experts at PANGAEA, all efforts have been made to publish iAtlantic's research results through open access channels and to ensure that project datasets are archived according to the highest data curation standards.

Pushing data management standards beyond the boundaries of iAtlantic, the data management team worked to fully integrate the South African Environmental Observation Network (NRF-SAEON) data catalogue system with the Global Earth Observing System of Systems, GEOSS. The GEOSS Portal is a global initiative and ensures a global reach, addressing the widest possible number of users and stakeholders. This successful integration with has enabled NRF-SAEON to assume the role of primary research data repository for data publications by iAtlantic and other All-Atlantic projects in the South Atlantic region - a significant milestone in improving the visibility and accessibility of South Atlantic data resources.

Pushing this philosophy further, iAtlantic was part of an international initiative to build an All-Atlantic Ocean Data (AAOD) community portal on the GEOSS Portal. The AAOD was launched in December 2021, aiming to consolidate, strengthen and grow the international Atlantic observing community. Today, the AAOD has successfully integrated a long list of Atlantic data resources and is currently developing into a one-stop web portal to find and retrieve a unique breadth of openly available Atlantic research data and observation resources, including those from iAtlantic and other All-Atlantic projects.

iAtlantic also made important progress towards the transfer of the large and diverse PANGAEA data resources to the different thematic portals of the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet). Through a combination of implementing Web Mapping Services (WMS), establishing new workflows and improving data interoperability, various types of data (marine physics, biology, chemistry and bathymetry) can now be made centrally available via EMODnet. This represents a highly complex technical task involving significant changes to established protocols in both systems and can be considered a great success that will continue to be built on.

The iAtlantic GeoNode

To support the development of transparent basin-scale management scenarios for the whole Atlantic Ocean, iAtlantic developed and maintained an advanced Geospatial Information System (GIS) web platform to visualise the data collated and processed by the project: the iAtlantic GeoNode (www.geonode.iatlantic.eu). This platform, based on the open-source GeoNode software, provides a modern interface that allows users to search for, visualise and download geospatial data layers and combine them into interactive web maps and dashboards that can be shared and embedded in other websites. Furthermore, it makes geospatial datasets and their metadata interoperable with other applications through standard Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) web services.

As well as ingesting the geospatial datasets generated by the project (cruises, experiments, model simulations etc), the iAtlantic GeoNode team compiled existing relevant geospatial information from public repositories and contributions from industry partners. This comprises data layers of environmental information under present and future conditions, geomorphology and derivative data, observed and modelled species occurrence, existing spatial designations and management tools, areas exploited by industry (e.g., fishing effort, shipping), and areas of interest to industry (e.g., deep-sea mining), among others. In addition, existing open-source data from public marine data services (e.g. EMODnet, PANGAEA, Copernicus Marine Service, NOAA, IFREMER and many more) are remotely coupled to the GeoNode, and the GeoNode offers connections to many wider marine data services, documentation and maps. Now populated with 386 (and counting) geospatial datasets from many different sources, the iAtlantic GeoNode covers a diversity of topics including biogeography, biology, physical environment, management and conservation areas, human use and climate-driven projections.

www.geonode.iatlantic.eu

Figure 26: The GeoNode portal

Sharing knowledge, building capacity

In the field of marine science – and particularly deep-sea science – the inequities in scientific capacities between global North and global South are marked. Deep-sea scientific research is an expensive endeavour, requiring long-term national (and sometimes regional) investment in education, research facilities, technology and infrastructure supported by strong socio-political will. Today, more than ever, a concerted, collaborative and unified approach is required to generate the knowledge and data needed to address the many challenges and threats affecting the global ocean.

Almost without exception, sustainable development and environmental conservation strategies at international, regional and – in many parts of the world – national levels clearly identify the urgent need for capacity development.

In the Atlantic region, capacity building is implicit in both the Belém Statement and the South-South Framework for Scientific and Technical Cooperation in the South and Tropical Atlantic and Southern Oceans. The Belém Statement calls for activities “*optimising the appropriate use and sharing of research infrastructures, and access to and management of data and platforms; together with emerging methods of data science*” as well as efforts to “*promote and facilitate human capital development and scientific exchange*”.

Recognising the importance of human and technical capacities in underpinning a truly collaborative and inclusive approach to basin-scale marine science, iAtlantic placed capacity building at the core of its mission with a comprehensive programme aiming to share knowledge, infrastructure, equipment and expertise across the project partnership. The iAtlantic capacity building programme encompassed hands-on training at sea and in the laboratory, through formal instruction and training events, as well as through more informal individual coaching and mentoring approaches, online learning opportunities and a fully inclusive approach to the research process – including the transfer of knowledge to end users.

Central to the programme’s activities was the iAtlantic Fellowship, comprising the cohort of 50+ early career researchers associated with the project, who really provided the scientific horsepower in iAtlantic’s engine. Inclusion of the Fellows in all aspects of the project was central to the project’s approach, underpinning its ambition to produce the next generation of marine science leaders. However, learning opportunities were open to researchers at all career levels and – wherever possible – opened to suitable participants from the wider Atlantic research community.

A series of technical capacity building and training workshops (both online and in person) were organised for researchers within the project and beyond, to support their research and broaden their skill base in recognition of the increasingly multidisciplinary nature of marine science in today’s world. Covering topics from every part of iAtlantic’s work programme, these 16 workshops included training on taxonomy, data processing, numerical and statistical modelling, time series analysis, hydroacoustics, ocean governance, seafloor surveying and specialist laboratory techniques (Fig. 29). More informal learning opportunities were offered through a regular webinar series, which were open to everyone and are now available to view through iAtlantic’s video archive. These webinars also became an important way of building connections for our team during the COVID19 pandemic.

Seagoing experience is a hugely important element in developing careers of marine scientists and technicians, not only in terms of successful sampling and data collection from a research vessel, but also in the planning, processes and logistics involved in executing a successful sea-going expedition. iAtlantic’s capacity building programme encompassed the full suite of offshore survey and sampling techniques used in multidisciplinary research expeditions, including pre-cruise planning, sampling strategies, experimental design, contingency planning, and shadowing of principal scientists during cruises – all essential skills for the next generation of expedition leaders. Wherever possible, berths for ECRs were secured on iAtlantic expeditions, and in 2021 a dedicated flagship

Figure 27 (right): iMirabilis2 expedition participants undergo safety drill training aboard RV Sarmiento de Gamboa. Image courtesy K. Archer Barnhill.

Figure 28: The BR10 expedition team – nearly all of whom were ECRs – aboard the Brazilian Navy vessel RV Vital de Oliveira, before heading out to undertake seafloor mapping in the Santos Basin offshore Brazil, December 2022.

capacity building expedition, iMirabilis2 (Fig. 27), provided extensive at-sea training for early career researchers – not only for those on board the ship but also for those back on land, through the innovative ‘Ship-to-Shore’ buddy scheme. Here, participants on board the research vessel partnered with ECRs back on land, sharing their experiences via daily video and messaging communication. This allowed the virtual participation of researchers from Brazil, Cabo Verde, Columbia, Ghana, South Africa and Togo, as well as from

institutions in Europe and North America. iAtlantic also provided support for South Africa’s SEAmester programme, which offers an annual seagoing training expedition board RV *Agulhas* for young scientists from the SE Atlantic region (main picture, p35; Fig. 24).

Capacity development in iAtlantic included more than training and teaching. Sharing of infrastructure and equipment, creating access to facilities, data and know-how, and providing opportunities for researcher mobility between partner institutions were championed in recognition of their importance in achieving a fully inclusive approach to the research questions iAtlantic set out to tackle.

Considerable effort was also devoted to enhancing and expanding technological capacities. Technological advancements in the fields of seafloor imaging, data processing, artificial intelligence, eDNA sampling and machine learning were achieved during the project (p39). iAtlantic funding supported the expansion of oceanographic monitoring capabilities in the South Atlantic (p10) and the transfer of low-cost video surveying technology – including training on its assembly, operation and maintenance, as well as on the processing of image data collected – to researchers in Brazil and South Africa (p39).

iAtlantic provided fertile ground for innovation, not only across the Atlantic region but also between scientific sub-disciplines. The highly multi- and interdisciplinary nature of the project provided impetus for adaptation of techniques and approaches to solve new research questions at a variety of scales, many of which are described in detail in the earlier sections of this report.

Figure 29: iAtlantic technical training workshops included cold-water coral taxonomy (left) and the assembly and operation of the Azor drift-cam (right).

Working with stakeholders

An essential component of research in today's world is the timely communication of results and outcomes beyond the scientific community, so that new information can be taken up in key policy discussions and used to support effective decision-making and improve management practices. Engagement with stakeholders and end-users of new science during the course of research (not just at the end) is essential to maximise the relevance, uptake and impact of results.

iAtlantic established a clear strategy to share knowledge, outcomes and results with a broad range of audiences throughout the project's life cycle. Through a series of stakeholder dialogue events, we brought together project scientists and representatives from specific sectors and communities to discuss emerging results and their implications for stakeholder agendas. The first such event took place in the margins of the UN Ocean Conference in June 2022, targeting the NGO and civil society community. This was followed by a second event at the European Parliament in March 2023, hosted by MEP Isabel Carvalhais as part of the European Parliament Intergroup on Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Development. Titled *'Science advances at the ocean-climate-biodiversity nexus: Highlights from the Atlantic'* this event focused on showcasing complementary results and key messages from iAtlantic and sister H2020 projects TRIATLAS and AtlantECO to Members of the European Parliament.

Figure 31: iAtlantic has produced briefing documents summarising specific policy-relevant results. See www.iatlantic.eu/resources

The final iAtlantic project meeting, held in Edinburgh in October 2023, was conceived as an open conference to provide maximum exposure to the achievements and outcomes of iAtlantic research. Attracting participants from policy, industry and NGO sectors, as well as from the wider scientific community, the programme included stakeholder panel sessions to reflect on the science impact and policy relevance of iAtlantic's results.

iAtlantic also sought to engage directly with relevant operational groups, competent authorities, policy processes and regional organisations. This activity ranged from bilateral meetings to discuss specific aspects of iAtlantic's research (e.g., OSPAR, FAO), to working with industry groups to share data and knowledge (e.g., IOGP, Petrobras, Icelandic fishing groups), and more informal gatherings such as iAtlantic's evening showcase event during UNFCCC COP26 (Fig. 30) and a side event at the UN Ocean Conference in 2022. iAtlantic partners actively participated in international ocean policy meetings such as the Intergovernmental Conferences leading up to the adoption of the new UN treaty to protect biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction (BBNJ), meetings of the various UN FAO fisheries committees and reviews, relevant workshops convened by the CBD on the development and implementation off the Global Biodiversity Framework, selected meetings of the UN Regular Process, and the sessions at the International Seabed Authority to develop seabed mining regulations. iAtlantic has sought opportunities to provide new and relevant scientific information to these processes, including through contributing to public stakeholder consultations and publishing briefing documents on specific policy-relevant topics (Fig. 31).

Figure 30: Guests gather under the Gaia art installation at the iAtlantic stakeholder evening event during UNFCCC COP26, November 2021.

Technology and innovation

In parallel with data collation, new observations, data analyses and map production, iAtlantic invested major effort in advancing technologies to make ecosystem mapping and assessment faster, cheaper, more accessible and more efficient.

Environmental DNA sampling

The Robotic Cartridge Sampling Instrument (RoCSI) enables *in situ* filtering and preservation of predefined volumes of seawater for the collection of genetic material such as environmental DNA (eDNA). RoCSI was progressed from Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5 to TRL 7 and was successfully demonstrated at >3000 m water depth, mounted in the Autosub6000 AUV, during the iMirabilis2 expedition (photo, right). The instrument was also deployed successfully on the new Autosub5 AUV in the Whittard Canyon, where it took samples in parallel with traditional habitat mapping techniques (photography, acoustic mapping) to investigate the extent of the eDNA signature of the benthic community. The RoCSI technology has now been acquired by McLane Research Laboratories Inc. and will be marketed by them.

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The Azor drift-cam low-cost video survey system

The Azor drift-cam low-cost camera system was developed as an affordable and easy-to-use underwater video system, designed for a rapid appraisal of benthic habitats down to 1000 m water depth. Through iAtlantic, it was progressed from TRL6 to TRL7. The system is built with off-the-shelf components, and thanks to public release of specifications (Dominguez-Carrio et al. 2021), it can be assembled by research groups all over the world. Throughout the course of the project, more than 450 hours of video data were collected with the Azor drift-cam, often deployed from vessels of opportunity. Training on the construction and operation of the system was a key event in iAtlantic's capacity building programme, facilitating the transfer of technology to South Atlantic institutions.

High-resolution 3D imaging

We used 3D high-resolution imaging to investigate the scale patterns and faunal dynamics at deep-sea vents. As our scientific perception of natural systems has been highly constrained by technological limits, these new methods can be used to expand ecological characterisation across various spatial and temporal scales. An example is the analysis of images acquired daily over 7 years with the TEMPO underwater camera connected to the deep-sea EMSO-Azores observatory at the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (right), which has revealed the vent habitat and associated vent mussel assemblage to be highly stable. We also accurately unravelled the dynamics of vent assemblages over the 450-m² Tour Eiffel hydrothermal edifice with a resolution of a few cm despite the complex topography. This 5-year time series confirmed the high stability of the vent communities.

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Image FAIR Digital Objects

A major step forward (TRL2 to TRL 7) was also achieved in the development of FAIR marine image metadata standards. The iFDOs (image FAIR Digital Objects) proposed by Schoening et al. (2022) were designed to be applied to all types of marine image data (in-situ or ex-situ, video or stills, single images or datasets of thousands of photographs), and will enable users to address all necessary requirements of data FAIRness in a structured and coherent way.

Hyperspectral imaging

iAtlantic also saw the first tests of hyperspectral imaging in the deep sea, aimed at the identification of benthic habitats and assessment of habitat ecological status, particularly in cold-water coral reefs. While hyperspectral cameras are proven technology, their implementation in deep-water marine robotics is new, opening up new perspectives for ecosystem mapping and assessment. Initial results showed different hyperspectral signatures for different cold-water coral species, and for live and dead coral framework. Machine learning algorithms were able to detect these signatures, enabling automated benthic mapping and demonstrating that this technology has potential for the automated extraction of relevant deep-sea environmental information and for future ecosystem monitoring.

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COMMA toolbox

The Confined Morphologies Mapping (CoMMA) toolbox is a new ArcGIS Pro toolbox to semi-automatically map and characterise confined landforms such as cold-water coral mounds, pockmarks and drumlins. The toolbox includes three toolsets that allow users to pre-process multi-beam data and calculate local topographic parameters, delineate potential features, and describe the morphological characteristics of confined features. The extracted morphometric data can be used to understand spatial patterns in shape, biodiversity and environmental conditions of seabed features such as cold-water coral mounds across the ocean. An open-access user guide and online tutorial are currently being developed by the project team.

3D virtual reconstruction of cold-water corals

Studies have shown that stressors from global change are likely to affect the ecophysiological processes and performance (e.g., skeletal growth, respiration, excretion rates) of cold-water corals. The 3D virtual reconstructions made possible with this new tool help us better understand and evaluate the effects of climate change on the ecophysiology of corals under laboratory conditions. This low-cost tool efficiently captures high-quality photos of corals at several angles over 360° (see photo, right), allowing for 3D virtual reconstructions. This imagery has multiple uses, such as continuous monitoring of tissue regeneration or retraction, changes in the tissue structure and measurement of growth.

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Impact and relevance

iAtlantic was conceived in response to the EU's Horizon 2020 call for projects to help implement the Belém Statement – a joint Declaration on Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Cooperation between the European Union, Brazil and South Africa. Designed and planned as a fully collaborative North-South research initiative, iAtlantic set out an ambitious suite of objectives that not only sought to push forward scientific understanding of deep Atlantic ecosystems, but also provide meaningful results with relevance for decision-making, planning and sustainable management of marine resources – with different aspects of our work relevant at local, regional and ocean basin scale (Roberts et al. 2023). As iAtlantic draws to a close after nearly 5 years of intensive work, we reflect on the project's impact and the contributions it has made to the work of a wide range of stakeholders.

The impact of iAtlantic's work can be considered in the following contexts:

Generating knowledge to fill gaps in our understanding of deep-sea and open-ocean ecosystems: distribution, dynamics, vulnerability and response to multiple threats such as climate change and human activities.

Developing **new technologies and techniques** to help supply missing information and knowledge: survey tools, sample processing techniques, innovative ways of handling and manipulating marine data.

Providing underpinning infrastructure to **support and facilitate access to data**: common data standards, open access data repositories, better connections between existing facilities and communities.

Actioning the **transfer of new scientific knowledge** and know how to stakeholders and end users – from scientific peers in other regions to international policy fora, and encompassing marine industries, regulatory authorities, national governments and conservation groups.

Supporting the training and development of the **next generation of deep-sea scientists** across the Atlantic region: widening opportunities, broadening participation, sharing knowledge, facilitating innovation.

Building and strengthening **international scientific collaboration**, partnerships and networks through research co-design, sharing of resources, data and equipment, and working towards common goals.

Raising public awareness of the importance of the ocean – and specifically the deep ocean – as the planet's life support system by improving ocean literacy.

Strengthening international scientific collaboration

International cooperation has been at the heart of iAtlantic's approach. The consortium comprises nearly 200 researchers from 16 countries, and it is this breadth of expertise and experience, combined with a strong team dynamic, collective ambition to achieve the project goals, and ability to seek out innovative solutions to research challenges that has driven the success of the project. The enabling framework of the Belém Statement provided opportunities to forge new research relationships between north, south, east and west regions of the Atlantic basin, and reinforce and enhance long-term scientific collaborations, such as those around the oceanographic mooring arrays in the north (OSNAP), south (SAMOC-SAMBA) and south-west (SAMBA-west) Atlantic.

iAtlantic researchers forged bonds with many institutions, scientists and research groups outside the formal project partnership – too many to name here, but all contributing to a strengthened international marine science research community. iAtlantic took an active role in hosting events to launch the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development as well as subsequent events organised by the Decade's Early Career Ocean Professionals group. We had strong representation at events of the All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance, including the All Atlantic Forum meetings. And in 2022, iAtlantic was proud to host a side event on 'Scaling up ambition in science partnerships to address challenges at ocean basin scale: examples from the iAtlantic project', featuring high-level speakers from the EU, USA and Canada – all of whom highlighted the

importance of international scientific collaboration, through projects like iAtlantic, in tackling the triple planetary crisis of climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss.

Responding to an evolving policy landscape

During the project's lifetime, a number of new policy initiatives, agreements and designations have changed the shape of ocean governance in the Atlantic region. iAtlantic has followed these developments closely, participating at relevant meetings and promoting the role of science in decision-making, as well as seeking opportunities to feed specific project results into these processes.

In the international policy arena, parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) adopted the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) in December 2022, comprising a new set of agreed global biodiversity targets to be achieved by 2030, replacing the CBD's Aichi Biodiversity Targets that expired in 2020. iAtlantic's work has direct relevance for 9 of the 23 new GBF targets, which tackle spatial planning, ecosystem restoration, protected areas, adverse impacts, sustainable exploitation, climate change, management and use of wild species, pollution, sustainable fisheries and ecosystem services. A policy brief examining the relevance and application of iAtlantic results to the new GBF targets (Boteler et al. 2023) was published in December 2023, and was submitted as part of iAtlantic's response to the CBD's call for tools and guidance for Global Biodiversity Framework implementation (CBD Notification 2023/120; November 2023).

Figure 32: Dr John Bell, Director 'Healthy Planet', Directorate-General for Research & Innovation at the European Commission, presents at the iAtlantic side event at the UN Ocean Conference in Lisbon, June 2022.

Figure 33: Participants at Dynamic Earth in Edinburgh for the 2-day symposium 'The High Seas Treaty: from negotiation to implementation' in October 2023.

Also in December 2022, CBD Parties at COP15 approved 17 new ecologically or biologically significant marine areas (EBSAs) in the North-East Atlantic, adding to the international portfolio of EBSAs worldwide, which already includes areas in the SW and SE Atlantic. Whilst EBSAs confer no management obligations, they signal relative significance of an area for its conservation value. For many of these areas, empirical data is limited and their significance has been inferred based on bathymetry and other proxies and analogues. iAtlantic outputs will help strengthen and update EBSA descriptions, contribute to any future discussions on the establishment of EBSAs in the Atlantic region, and help to inform the positions of States. iAtlantic has worked closely with the CBD Secretariat throughout the course of the project, responding to calls for information and presenting scientific findings on ecosystem connectivity at a side event at CBD COP15.

In a landmark moment for high seas protection, in June 2023 parties to the United Nations agreed a new treaty on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction (the BBNJ Agreement, or High Seas Treaty). Having followed the treaty negotiation process closely over the preceding 10 or more years, members of the iAtlantic team were well placed to seize an opportunity to lead the organisation of a 2-day symposium 'The High Seas Treaty: From negotiation to implementation'. Involving more than 500 participants in person and online, the symposium provided a neutral space to bring together more than 100 organisations from 50+ nations to discuss the opportunities and challenges in transitioning this historic agreement from negotiation to implementation.

The event offered a collective statement from participants that welcomed the BBNJ Agreement and recognised its importance in safeguarding the health and sustainability of the global ocean and marine biodiversity, as well as expressing participants' firm and collective commitment to its future implementation. A variety of outputs are expected from the event as well as future events building on the outcomes of this initial gathering of the BBNJ community.

The GBF, BBNJ Agreement and other relevant international agreements and frameworks are set against the backdrop of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). SDG14, Life Under Water, calls for advances in marine scientific knowledge and increases in capacity to provide the information needed to improve ocean health, support the sustainable management and protection of marine and coastal ecosystems to avoid significant adverse impacts, strengthen their resilience and inform restoration actions, and sets a minimum 10% protected area target for coastal and marine areas, based on the best available scientific information. The new knowledge generated through iAtlantic directly contributes to these objectives, as well as indirectly supporting progress towards SDG14 targets focused on economic benefits and development of developing countries, in particular Small Island Developing States and least developed countries.

Bringing the focus to a regional lens, iAtlantic has worked closely with the OSPAR Commission to help advance protection for deep-sea ecosystems in the north-east Atlantic. The North Atlantic Current and Evlanov Sea Basin Marine Protected Area (NACES MPA) was designated

by OSPAR in 2021 to protect seabirds over an area of c. 600,000 km² but included only the water column. A subsequent proposal to extend protection to the seafloor included a large volume of biological and environmental data contributed by iAtlantic, including fast-tracked sample analyses from iAtlantic expeditions such as IceDIVA2, and information on biological connectivity between seafloor and water column. The proposal was successful and the MPA extension approved by OSPAR Parties in June 2023. iAtlantic scientists also input to OSPAR's 2023 Quality Status Review (QSR2023 - a 10-year assessment of the environmental status of the North East Atlantic), providing specialist knowledge on the status of carbonate mound habitats.

iAtlantic is also relevant to the European Green Deal (EGD), a set of policy initiatives launched by the European Commission in December 2019 to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The EGD recognises that enhanced international cooperation will be needed to address common global challenges such as climate, pollution, and biodiversity loss and seeks to strengthen the EU's partnerships with other regions and countries, supporting a multilateral approach. This links to the EU Global Ocean Governance Strategy 2022, relating to green diplomacy and global leadership. Regarding biodiversity more specifically, iAtlantic results can be critical to inform the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and its Action Plan as well as related EU policies. Specific biodiversity targets include protecting a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrating ecological corridors, as well as establishing strict protection of at least a third of the EU's protected areas (EU Biodiversity Strategy), restoring areas of degraded and carbon rich ecosystems, and protecting habitats and species (EU Habitats Directive), as well as substantially reducing negative impacts on sensitive species and habitats, including on the seabed, through fishing and extraction activities to reach a good environmental status (GES) (EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive). These issues were touched upon during iAtlantic's stakeholder dialogue event at the European Parliament in March 2023.

Further south, iAtlantic has worked extensively with the Sargasso Sea Commission, one of iAtlantic's Associate Partners. New knowledge generated by iAtlantic in the Sargasso Sea region is feeding into the Commission's Socio-Ecosystem Diagnostic Analysis - an exercise to identify, quantify, and set priorities for environmental problems that threaten the long-term integrity and sustainability of the ecosystem.

At a national level, iAtlantic has contributed important data and analyses to planning and conservation initiatives, ranging from providing new seafloor survey data to support national planning exercises (Cabo Verde, Bermuda) to

Figure 34: All Atlantic project partners in Brussels ahead of the European Parliament stakeholder event organised by iAtlantic in March 2023. From left to right: Noel Keenlyside (TRIATLAS), Daniele Iudicone (AtlantECO), Vikki Gunn, Murray Roberts and David Johnson (iAtlantic).

assisting with systematic conservation planning (Azores, South Africa). iAtlantic results have also provided new insights relevant for national fisheries management (Iceland, Brazil), informed the scoping of potential new protective measures (Bermuda), and provided national delegates from many countries (including beyond the Atlantic region) with the latest scientific information to inform their positions at international policy meetings. In South Africa, extensive stakeholder dialogue has helped to shift the dial on conservation planning and expanding the national MPA network, with many lessons learned that can translate to other regions and countries. Among many achievements, iAtlantic's capacity development programme directly engaged researchers from west Africa, providing training in skills for national fisheries management; it provided new, low-cost video survey technology along with the necessary operational skills to researchers in Brazil and South Africa, and it has enabled the transfer of specialised expertise in cold-water coral taxonomy from Brazil to the European coral research community.

Contributing to sustainable Blue Growth

iAtlantic aimed to directly contribute the primary components – knowledge, tools and technologies – to support sustainable growth of ocean-based industries in the Atlantic: fisheries, aquaculture, the energy sector, mining, biotechnology, maritime and coastal tourism.

A key sector benefitting from the knowledge that iAtlantic has generated is the nascent deep-sea mining industry. Despite increasing interest in the potential mineral wealth offered by seabed mineral resources such as seafloor massive sulphides, polymetallic nodules and ferromanganese crusts, very little is known about the impacts that mining would have on benthic and pelagic ecosystems and habitats. iAtlantic’s extensive experimental work on multiple and cumulative stressors has generated important new results of direct relevance to the current topics under debate at the International Seabed Authority (ISA), the body responsible for regulating deep-sea mining activities in international waters. These results have been published in peer-reviewed journals and summarised in a series of science briefs specifically aimed at Parties to the ISA. iAtlantic representatives attended relevant ISA meetings over the course of the project, providing signposting and access to scientific resources to help inform decision-making, and the project has provided input to the ISA’s public stakeholder consultation exercises.

iAtlantic’s work on habitat prediction, distribution of vulnerable marine ecosystems, ecosystem recovery after disturbance, and the observed and expected impacts of climate change on pelagic ecosystems – including fish populations – have direct application to fisheries

management at international, regional and national scale. iAtlantic directly engaged with fisheries policy meetings at all levels, including at the UN General Assembly (UNGA) review of implementation of measures to address the impacts of bottom fishing on vulnerable marine ecosystems and the long-term sustainability of deep-sea fish stocks; supporting the EU in developing its proposals to the UNGA for enhanced management of deep-sea fisheries on the high seas to protect vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems, and providing results to the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and the European Commission to inform discussions on the implementation of the EU deep-sea fisheries Regulation 2016/2336 to protect vulnerable deep-sea marine ecosystems in EU waters from the impacts of bottom fishing, which culminated in some 16,000 km² of deep-sea areas in the Atlantic waters of the European Union being closed to bottom fishing to protect deep-sea benthic ecosystems. iAtlantic’s work was highlighted at the meeting of the Permanent Committee on Management and Science of the North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC), and results are relevant for the 5-year review of NEAFC’s bottom fisheries regulation (Recommendation 19/2014) scheduled to take place in 2024. iAtlantic scientists have contributed to discussion and advances in the management of highly migratory oceanic pelagic species from the Atlantic Ocean at meetings of the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tuna (ICCAT), and at a national level have highlighted the impacts and risks of climate change to fish stocks.

iAtlantic has worked closely with the oil and gas sector from the outset, building a strong partnership with the International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (IOGP) to help broker agreements between industry operators and scientists around the sharing of commercial environmental data. Thanks to liaison between iAtlantic’s Advisory Board and Petrobras, important seabed multibeam bathymetry data were made publicly available for the first time – a particularly important resource for Brazilian researchers working on ecosystem mapping and habitat characterisation. Discussions with Petrobras regarding decommissioning plans and future contributions to deep-sea coral research in the South Atlantic are underway at the time of writing.

iAtlantic was funded as part of a portfolio of research projects tackling different aspects of Atlantic marine science. Aquaculture issues were not part of iAtlantic’s remit but are the focus of other projects within the All Atlantic family, and iAtlantic has worked to ensure that relevant results have been shared with the AquaVitae and ASTRAL projects.

Figure 35: The Moose at Snake Pit hydrothermal vent field, 23°N on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Image courtesy Ifremer/Victor 6000, Bicosse cruise (2014)

Pushing the boundaries of marine innovation

iAtlantic committed to maximising the potential of its research results and innovative technologies to ensure a legacy of sustainability and support for a 'greener' blue economy that benefits the marine environment. The project has developed high quality instrumentation, techniques and software for use by the ocean science and management communities, offering potential to enhance research capabilities, create and secure opportunities for funding ambitious future research, and aid organisations working in marine management and the blue economy. Examples include the Azor drift-cam, which offers a straightforward solution to seafloor video surveying and is cost effective and easy to source, build, operate, deploy and maintain.

For countries and organisations that do not have access to ocean-going research vessels or highly advanced deep-sea survey technology such as ROVs, access to this technology provides the means to undertake marine surveying and monitoring at reasonable cost, with the necessary know-how on the system's components and construction freely available as an open-access paper. iAtlantic has also supported the development of RoCSI - an automated system that samples environmental DNA (eDNA). This instrument can characterise biological communities with high sensitivity and species-level accuracy without disturbing organisms and offers a way to characterise biological baselines or monitor conditions in remote environments that are often challenging to sample - for example, protected or sensitive areas located far offshore.

New habitat mapping and prediction techniques, species distribution models and machine learning protocols advanced under iAtlantic represent solid steps towards filling knowledge gaps in regions of the ocean that are under-surveyed. Reliably predicting where species and habitats occur, based on environmental characteristics and species traits, is vital in understanding likely future shifts in ecosystems as a consequence of climate change - a priority for many competent authorities with responsibility for sustainably managing and protecting ocean resources.

The systematic conservation planning methodology developed during the project also has significant potential in forecasting the impact of human activities and global change across Atlantic ecosystems, including the likely consequences that activities in areas beyond national jurisdiction might have on countries' exclusive economic zones, and in standardising approaches to the production of maps and management tools that facilitate comparisons across regions and improve management of common resources. Outcomes are also highly relevant to industries undertaking area-based management, including deep-sea mining operations, fisheries and future offshore aquaculture.

Training the next generation of deep-sea scientists

In the long term, iAtlantic's greatest legacy is the new generation of marine scientists who started their careers as part of the project team. More than 50 early career researchers across the Atlantic region, including MSc students, PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers and technicians, formed the iAtlantic Fellowship and will go on to be the ocean science leaders of the future. iAtlantic strived to maximise opportunities for this cohort to experience the best of international, multidisciplinary, cooperative science, aiming not only to reinforce the concept of collaborative team working as the best approach to solving scientific questions but also to set ambitiously high standards in equality, inclusivity, transparency and fairness. Despite the many challenges brought by the COVID19 pandemic, the iAtlantic Fellows forged new pathways in their fields of research and provided a large part of the scientific horsepower in iAtlantic's engine. Collectively they created a supportive and open-minded network of young professionals that will continue to push the boundaries of marine science well beyond the lifespan of iAtlantic.

Figure 36 (both images): iAtlantic Fellows formed an integral and vital part of the project team. Lower image courtesy B. Vinha / iMirabilis2.

Summary of iAtlantic impacts

<p>Contribution of new scientific knowledge to fill gaps in our understanding of deep-sea and open-ocean ecosystems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved ocean models at a range of scales to better understand the variability of AMOC in the past, present and future – and the impact of those changes on marine ecosystems. • New understanding of the role of ocean currents in the connectivity of specialised hydrothermal vent communities at the MAR. • Identification of key drivers of ecosystem change and potential tipping points in the deep and open ocean, based on time series data. • Identification of a tropicalisation trend in warm-water affinity species becoming more abundant across the Atlantic. • Better understanding of what effects changes in the upper ocean have on the deep ocean environment, including on the deep seabed's ability to sequester carbon. • Demonstration of the likely impacts of climate change and human activities on a range of deep-sea ecosystems, including effects of deep-sea mining on benthic and pelagic fauna (alone and in combination with climate change), impacts of pollution, ocean acidification and climate change on cold-water corals.
<p>Development of new technologies and techniques to help supply missing information and expand capabilities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New habitat suitability models to predict habitat and species shifts as a consequence of climate change, as well as new machine learning approaches to develop habitat maps at basin to local scale. • Advancement, demonstration and transfer of a low-cost video survey tool, eDNA sampler, new high-resolution imaging technologies, and mapping tools.
<p>Provision of underpinning infrastructure to support and facilitate access to marine data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of the iAtlantic GeoNode to support basin-scale conservation planning, allowing users to search for, visualise, download and share 370+ geospatial datasets. • Integrated the South African Environmental Observation Network (NRF-SAEON) data catalogue system with the Global Earth Observing System of Systems, GEOSS. • Catalysed the establishment of the All-Atlantic Ocean Data community portal on the GEOSS platform. • Progressing the transfer of data resources from PANGAEA to EMODnet thematic portals Development of Image FAIR Digital Objects (iFDOs).
<p>Facilitating the transfer of new scientific knowledge and know how to stakeholders and end users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of transparent ocean basin-scale management scenarios for the whole Atlantic, as well as at regional scales. • 100+ open access publications, 7 science/policy briefs, 200+ conference presentations. • iAtlantic open access Zenodo archive of all project outputs and publications. • 3 focused stakeholder dialogue events to share and discuss latest project results. • Participation in major ocean policy processes and events, including relevant meetings of the CBD, ISA, FAO, BBNJ, OSPAR, NEAFC, NAFO, ICES as well as national bodies. • Collaboration with marine industries – e.g., IOGP, fisheries bodies, marine tourism operators, subsea cable providers.
<p>Supporting the training and development of the next generation of deep-sea scientists across the Atlantic region</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of the iAtlantic Fellowship, comprising >50 early career researchers from the iAtlantic community. • 16 scientific capacity development workshops, 27 webinars. • At-sea training, researcher exchange, jointly supervised PhD/MSc students.
<p>Building and strengthening international scientific collaboration, partnerships and networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive project consortium spanning Europe, Brazil, South Africa, Argentina, Canada and the USA, complemented by a wider network of associated partners. • Broader regional and sectoral representation through Advisory Board and Science Council members. • Active participation in All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance events, UN Ocean Decade, UN Ocean Conference.
<p>Raising public awareness of the importance of the ocean</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong online presence via the iAtlantic website, social media accounts, plus bi-annual newsletters. • Extensive blog coverage of research expeditions through the course of the project. • Active participation in more than 50 public events, including 5 UN Ocean Decade events. • Production of 3 iAtlantic films that aim to share knowledge and results with a broad audience. • Publicity in the mainstream media on key ocean issues.

Parting words

As we built and designed iAtlantic we worked hard to co-develop our research priorities with as ocean stakeholders spanning national, regional and international levels. We are very grateful to everyone who has given their time and contributed so generously both to the initial planning and delivery of iAtlantic.

"iAtlantic's assessment of deep and open-ocean ecosystems and its steady building of capacity/technology transfer augur well for the ocean science results we seek. I commend iAtlantic's close involvement of Early Career Ocean Professionals and find it powerful news that iAtlantic has been getting that understanding directly into national, regional, and international policy processes."

Ambassador Peter Thomson, UN Secretary General's Special Envoy for the Ocean

"The state of the Atlantic Ocean will partly determine Europe's and Atlantic communities' sustainable future, its weather patterns, its overall relationship with partner countries, its prosperity and opportunities for our future generations. We still do not know much about all the possible changes, but with the many interesting and important results, the iAtlantic project has contributed to put a 'light' into the deep Atlantic Ocean. It demonstrated, on the field, how many of the joint achievements depended on international cooperation, but also on the tireless engagement and the enthusiasm of the whole project team."

Sieglinde Gruber, Former Head of the Healthy Ocean & Seas Unit, European Commission

"iAtlantic and the 2021 IceDivA2 expedition gave OSPAR valuable new information on the physical and biological processes that make the NACES marine protected area such a special place for seabirds and other animals. This 'North Atlantic Current and Evlanov Sea Basin' MPA is in the OSPAR Maritime Area (Region V, Wider Atlantic). The iAtlantic consortium's extensive knowledge of how the deep-seabed and water column are coupled made a much stronger case to expand the conservation objectives to protect and conserve a wider range of species, habitats and ecological processes – including the seabed. This highlights how fast we can now bring the latest discoveries and scientific understanding into management of areas beyond national jurisdiction."

Dominic Pattinson, Executive Secretary of the OSPAR Commission

"We became involved in iAtlantic from different backgrounds and perspectives. Yet we both agreed to do so on the basis of our personal knowledge of the calibre of its leadership; the ambitious research objectives of the proposal, using novel technologies to allow unprecedented collection of information on the deep-sea, and the impressive breadth of participation of countries and research centres. We therefore had high expectations for the project's scientific quality – that we are delighted to say have not only been met but exceeded. What we didn't expect five years ago (and no-one else did either) was the need for extraordinary resilience and flexibility to overcome the many challenges posed by Covid, including the disruption to fieldwork plans and the need to find new ways to meet and get to know each other. Nor did either of us expect to be as impressed as we were by the very great contribution of the early career scientists to the outputs, outcomes and overall success of iAtlantic. A lot of hard work was undoubtedly involved, yet also creativity and willingness to ask new questions, not just seek answers to old ones. Their enthusiasm and networking initiatives have strengthened iAtlantic immeasurably, through the community that formed among all the participants: young, middle-aged and old. Such a legacy will continue to generate knowledge and understanding of the ocean, for long after the actual data collected and papers published are looked at as 'interesting history, well done for its time'."

Phil Williamson, Chair of iAtlantic Advisory Board, and Jake Rice, Chair of iAtlantic Science Council

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For a full list of iAtlantic publications please see:
www.iatlantic.eu/our-work/publications/

iAtlantic maintains an open access archive of all project publications at zenodo.org/communities/iatlantic-project-collection

iAtlantic deliverables

Available online at: www.iatlantic.eu/our-work/deliverables

- D1.1 Atlantic circulation variability in the past 50 years
- D1.2 Ecosystem relevant variations and oceanographic trends from present day to 2070
- D1.3 Quantitative assessment of near-seafloor flow dynamics and physical drivers for material and larval transport
- D1.4 Oxygen measurements at the southern and northern boundaries of the AMOC
- D1.5 Preferential pathways of dispersal and role of the AMOC in connectivity
- D2.1 Basin-wide Atlantic marine landscape map
- D2.2 Models of VME taxa and functional traits distribution
- D2.3 3D habitat maps (point cloud models)
- D2.4 New imaging and analysis approaches for marine species detection and classification
- D2.5 VME taxa and functional trait predictions
- D2.6 Environmental drivers of ecosystem spatial patterns in the Atlantic
- D3.1 Methods to create and assess deep and open ocean timeseries
- D3.2 Drivers of ecosystem change and tipping points
- D3.3 Risk assessments of future changes to ecosystem dynamics and risk of tipping points
- D4.1 Stressor impacts on planktonic organisms
- D4.2 Baseline ecosystem function in selected deep pelagic and benthic environments
- D4.3 Assessment of the effects of multiple stressors on the functioning of hard-bottom VME ecosystems
- D4.4 Assessment of the effects of multiple stressors on the pelagic larvae of VME species
- D4.5 Impact of increased temperature, and altered POC composition on soft-sediment ecosystems
- D5.3 Ocean-scale management scenarios for the Atlantic
- D6.1 iAtlantic dissemination, exploitation and communication plan
- D6.2 Atlantic Ocean governance frameworks affecting Atlantic marine ecosystems under conditions of change
- D6.3 Outcomes of regional capacity building, enhancing skills development and knowledge transfer between the North and South Atlantic
- D6.4 Challenges and recommendations for Atlantic Ocean governance
- D6.5 Final exploitation plans for the result and outputs of the project
- D6.6 iAtlantic Research Highlights
- D7.2 GEOSS Atlantic Ocean Observation Community mirror site
- D7.3 Catalogue of iAtlantic Resources

iAtlantic science/policy briefs

Available online at: www.iatlantic.eu/resources

Acronyms

AAOD	All-Atlantic Ocean Data
ABMT	Area-based management tool
ABNJ	Area beyond national jurisdiction
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler conductivity profiler
AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
AUV	Autonomous underwater vehicle
BATS	Bermuda Atlantic time-series
BBNJ	Biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction
CBD	UN Convention on Biological Diversity
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CVAB	Cabo Verde Abyssal Basin
CVOO	Cabo Verde Ocean Observatory
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
EU	European Union
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable
FAO	UN Food and Agriculture Organization
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GIS	Geospatial information system
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
IOGP	International Association of Oil & Gas Producers
IWC	International Whaling Commission
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MAR	Mid-Atlantic Ridge
MPA	Marine protected area
MSP	Marine/maritime spatial planning
NASS	North Atlantic Sightings Surveys
NOAA	(US) National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRF-SAEON	National Research Foundation-South African Environmental Observation Network
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSNAP	Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Programme
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
PAP	Porcupine Abyssal Plain
PMS	Polymetallic sulphide
POC	Particulate organic carbon
RoCSI	Robotic Cartridge Sampling Instrument
ROV	Remotely operated vehicle
SAMBA	South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array
SAMOC	South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
SCP	Systematic conservation planning
TRL	Technology readiness level
UNFCCC	UN Framework Convention on Climate Change
VME	Vulnerable marine ecosystem
WMS	Web Map Service

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Associate partners

www.iatlantic.eu
i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk
[iAtlanticEU](#)

iAtlantic is part of the All Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Flagship
BUILDING AN ALL ATLANTIC OCEAN COMMUNITY
 Implementing the Belém Statement

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